

ISic2904

I.Sicily inscription 2904

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)**Place of origin (modern)**

Piazza Armerina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Piazza Armerina, in store

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI330705

1. Θ (εοῖς) Κ (αταχθονίοις) .
2. Ἰανάρια Φλωρέν-
3. τια, χρηστός καὶ
4. ἄμεμπτος, ἔζ[η]-
5. [σεν □ ἔτ]η □ με □ μῆ (νας) ζ
6. [ἡμέ(ρας)] ἦ', ὅς καὶ ἀκατάμ[ε]-
7. [μπ]τος □ ἰς γῆν ἔπο-
8. [ρεύ]θη· Βικτωρίνα Δω-
9. νάτα σεμνή καὶ ἀκ[α]-
10. τάγνωστ [ος(?) θ] εοῖς πρ[ο]-
11. [σ]φιλής [— — — — — — —]
- 12.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645297

EDCS 64800559

PHI 330705

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2005.0676

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 55.1016

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 32.0928

Gentili, G.V. 1952. I mosaici della villa romana del Casale di Piazza Armerina. *Bolletino d'Arte.* 37: 33-46. At 44 n.7

Pucci, G. 1971. Appendice IV. I materiali epigrafici del magazzino della villa del Casale.. *Mélanges de l'École Francaise de Rome: Antiquité.* 83: 249-260. At 251 fig.114

Manganaro, G. 1982. Die Villa von Piazza Armerina, Residenz des kaiserlichen Prokurators, und ein mit ihr verbundenes Emporium von Henna. In Papenfuss, D., Strocka, V.M.(eds.), *Palast und Hütte : Beiträge zum Bauen und Wohnen im Altertum von Archäologen, Vor- und Frühgeschichtlern: Tagungsbeiträge eines Symposiums der Alexander von Humboldt-Stiftung, Bonn-Bad Godesberg, veranstaltet vom 25.-30. November 1979 in Berlin.* Mainz. pp. 493-513. At 506 no.12 fig.19-20

Manganaro, G. 2005. Note storiche ed epigrafiche per la villa (praetorium) del Casale di Piazza Armerina. *Sicilia Antiqua.* 2: 173-191. At 186 fig.27-27bis

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic2904. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4387723>